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SOCIAL NETWORK: A FACTOR SHAPING THE IMAGE OF A HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTION

Description: *The article reveals the role of social networks in improving the reputation of higher educational institutions. Current trends of increasing competition in the academic space make the need for higher education institutions to use all possible means of modern media communications urgent. It is based on the fact that the creation of an information platform and a communicative environment on the Internet can also be implemented with advertising tools. Modern technical capabilities prove that they have a great benefit in image formation not only in the field of business, but also in higher educational institutions. While websites were in turn copies of print ads and catalogs, today they have become an image-building communication tool. However, it should be noted that the Internet is a fundamentally different communication medium. One branch of online journalism that has expanded its scope is mobile blogging. In the article, a study of higher educational institutions of the CIS, which have begun to access the possibilities of mobile journalism, is made. The article studied, compared, differentiated, and analyzed the methods of social networks in the field of real journalism of higher educational institutions for image formation.*

Keywords: *CIS, mobile blog, journalism, communication, social network, mobile journalism.*

Introduction

In the 21st century, there is a rapid increase in the number of social network users. According to datareportal.com, 4.74 billion people [1]. Most of them are 16-24 years old, so the target audience is school graduates and students. It shows that social networks play a significant role in forming a positive image of society using information resources.

Significant use of new resources and technologies in building the reputation of higher educational institutions, in order to attract applicants as much as possible. One of them is the social network. In order to maintain and increase the competitiveness of higher educational institutions, it is necessary to adhere to the classical market principle. J. Scholten: «Two factors are important for the survival of an organization in today's world: to be good and to stand out.»

In this regard, the effect of the mobile blog in creating an informational and communicative environment of higher educational institutions in the CIS countries was studied. Since the blogosphere is rapidly developing, the research was carried out to examine how much higher education institutions master this field and how it is used in image formation.

In order for the blogosphere to work normally in image formation, the social network must perform significant tasks:

- Considers the possibility of creating a virtual personality and flexible management of the mobile blog object. Through its speed and quality, it can form an idea about the object to the public.

- Enables two-way communication. Familiarity in the offline environment is not important, on the contrary, the main need is to establish a connection with a distant and close environment.

Features of the communication model of blogs provide information communication on mobile blogs and contribute to the organization of public discussions, thanks to which not only a certain public opinion on topics is formed, but in some cases specific measures to solve problems are used.

When considering the spread of information on a mobile blog as a means of communication, it is of great importance to know the weight of a certain blog in shaping the image of the social network in which it is located. It should be noted that the relative weight is not always obvious to an external observer. Having a map of social connections within your network is an even greater advantage. Proper management of a mobile blog and social network in higher educational institutions will lead to its popularity. It makes a huge contribution to sharing changes and news in the field of education and science, increasing the number of students, entering the world market, as well as working among commercial, political, public organizations and religious associations, and building reputation.

Methodology of research. Management and promotion of the information and communication environment of higher educational institutions through the network is becoming widespread. In our research work, several well-known higher educational institutions of the CIS were taken into account. Their mobile blog applications were studied based on their Instagram, YouTube, and Facebook pages. In addition to social analysis, the methodological basis of this study included theoretical methods of scientific knowledge. Methods of information synthesis and analysis, comparative method, method of systematic data analysis were used in the work, as well as a review of literary sources on this issue.

The social survey was conducted among foreign students of Kazakh National University named after Al-Farabi. And as a result of the online social survey in Kazakhstan, the southern, central and northern territories of the country were covered. On the basis of a social survey, the methods of using the interface, visual content, text content, infographics and artificial intelligence features of the web pages of the mentioned educational institutions were determined.

Using the method of comparative analysis, attention was paid to the online activity of national universities. Similarities and differences were identified in terms of information dissemination, visual content, and live broadcast professionalism. In particular, Kazakh National University named after Al-Farabi, Moscow State University named after MV Lomonosov, National University of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulugbek, Kyrgyz National University named after Yusup Balasaguni.

Such an analysis needs to cover the entire range of the page. However, in the course of the research, the faculty/department leaflets, which train real journalism specialists, were considered as the main object. Based on that, a review of the pages of other faculties/departments was made and joint decisions were made. Using the benchmarking method, a comparative analysis with Kazakhstani higher educational institutions was made.

Using the bibliometric method, the indicators of publication activity of Kazakhstani and foreign universities were analyzed.

As a result of the study, the scope of application of mobile journalism and online journalism in forming the image of higher educational institutions in the country was determined. Conclusions were made as a result of direct analysis of the pages of each educational institution. Based on that, many recommendations and applications were written in the article as specific guidelines.

Results and conclusions.

When conducting research on mobile blogs of higher education institutions, you cannot limit yourself to Instagram, as you will not be able to get complete information. However, access to general information on the site is also available on mobile devices. In this context, the top ten higher education institutions in the country have formed their own image, and their web pages are developing well.

The web pages of several higher educational institutions that were targeted were examined. When we review those pages, we make sure that the avatar displayed on the page is 100 percent consistent with the brand of the higher education institution. The main information is 30 percent, the style of the page is 20 percent, and the level of information provided in the form of a post is only 40 percent [Kudaybergenova R.E., Smagulov K.E., Omiralieva G.K., 2021, 95 p.].

One of my favorite ways to blog on mobile is to send email messages to your WordPress blog. WordPress creates a unique address for all email messages to prevent spam, or more precisely, block email. In this case, the title of the post appears in the email header, and the body text in the body of the email. An efficient way to search the main text by title. This is also necessary for statistics. Since statistics are the main indicator in working with advertising agencies in this case, it is possible to create a system for it.

Content creation with short form videos is the current demand for mobile blogging. Most video footage is now created by grouping images. There is reason to say that this, in turn, is a new approach, milestone, and a type of development. At this point, you can start photoblogging with Flickr. Flickr is a service for storing digital photos and videos and using them anytime. This app will be very popular in 2007. Along with MySpace, Facebook, Blogger, and YouTube, Flickr has been considered a forerunner of the Web 2.0 era [Maulen D., 2023]. However, now the world has moved to Instagram. Our research and reviews are also based on these web pages. However, the demand for Flickr can increase as it can store photos and videos in digital form. Even if the world does not completely switch to this application, it will be rational to use it as a high-quality image repository.

As a result of a comparative study on the effectiveness of networks, the most effective are the WordPress (effective for blog) and Telegram (social network and effective for blog) platforms (Figure 1). According to sources, 43.3 percent of all sites in the world work on the WordPress platform [Vroblevskiy L., 2012, 76.].

Source: trends.builtwith.com

Fig.1. WordPress Popular Countries Data

In the new trend of today's media, it is necessary to move to web applications rather than mobile applications, mobile blogs. Web applications are applications that can be used on a smartphone, tablet or computer without downloading and installing. In this case, the user's device can access the data online without having to install the application in the permanent memory. Examples of web applications are the aforementioned e-mail (Gmail) and text editors (Google Docs).

The reputation and self-promotion of universities on social networks and media platforms is different. On the basis of the research, starting from the personal websites of several universities, social network pages were taken as the main object.

The main site of Al-Farabi Kazakh National University provides links to 6 social networks [5]. You can go directly to Instagram and YouTube from the university website. Both pages are active. Especially when you connect to the YouTube channel, the video immediately opens, it captivates the person. As a result, the reader does not immediately leave the page, but continues to watch. This is a smart way to keep the audience.

One of the most popular higher educational institutions in the CIS is M.V. Lomonosov Moscow State University. The 270th anniversary of the university founded

in 1755 is planned to be celebrated next year. We can see it from the timer that stands out from the first visit to the site. This is different from the website of some higher educational institutions, and the news is displayed. News is updated daily and divided into sections. Data on the number of students, foreign students, and teachers at the university are shown. In the «Announcement» section, upcoming events are shown and the purpose and meaning are written. At the bottom of the site, it is divided into sections «applicant, student, master's degree, candidate of science, educators», you can access the desired information by scrolling. 5 networks are actively working [6]. The pages are developing very rapidly.

The main site of the Kyrgyz National University named after YusupBalasaguni has links to 3 social networks, 2 of which are active [7]. There is no video playing or special visuals. We consider this as the fact that no prerequisites are made for the reader to stay on the page. It is not easy to immediately find information for students and graduates on the site. Another thing worth noting is the link to the old site. If there is no «old» name, the information is updated daily. Because the main direction of the site is news. Access to certain information is quite difficult for site users. More links and information like other university sites would be attractive.

On the website of the National University of Uzbekistan named after MirzoUlugbek, more attention is paid to the history and external image of the university. Go to YouTube through the link and watch a video about the university from the university channel. And the achievements of the lower university in the international arena are shown in statistical terms. The inscriptions on the site are also very simple, in Uzbek and relatively give the impression of visiting the online version of a printed newspaper. 4 networks are actively working [8].

The ranking of first-rate national universities and other universities is as follows:

Al-Farabi Kazakh National University

YouTube: <https://youtube.com/@farabimedia-kaznu> 47,4K followers

Instagram: https://instagram.com/farabi_university 30,9K followers

Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/FarabiKaznu> 75 followers

Moscow State University named after M.V. Lomonosov

VK: https://vk.com/msu_official 124,5K followers

Telegram: <https://t.me/naukamsu%2012,2> 75K followers

YouTube: https://youtube.com/@msu?si=yorJBovf-FVF_jY2 31,5K followers

Rutube: <https://rutube.ru/channel/23642102/> 194 followers

Дзен: https://dzen.ru/msu_official?share_to=link 11,4K followers

Kyrgyz National University named after Yusup Balasaguni

Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/kg.knu?mibextid=LQQJ4d> 920followers

YouTube: <https://youtube.com/@jeenbek-eraliev?si=5p-6pbkWnnvXPM8u>
17,9K followers

National University of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulugbek

Telegram: https://t.me/nuu_uz 9286followers

Instagram: <https://www.instagram.com/nuu.uz?igsh=c2d5dTVnMXpwN3Zj>
4879 followers

Facebook: <https://m.facebook.com/nationaluniversityuzbekistan> 600 followers

YouTube: <https://youtube.com/@NationalUniversityofUzbekistan?si=zqTLEvLeVF00ANad> 7,2K followers

Feature of material transfer

Taking into account the communicative features of the medium, the style of providing material in online journalism has changed. The main principles of «online text» are determined by the features of information reception.

Online media reader behavior is quite different from that of traditional print consumers. Research shows that most website visitors want to quickly read the text. The reason for this is, first of all, a large array of information from which the user must choose what he really needs. The network provides an interactive environment where users exchange various information using hyperlinks. Secondly, these are problems of visual perception of information from the Internet publication. It is known that reading text on a screen is about 25% slower than reading text in print. This is why people shy away from reading large amounts of text on a screen. As a rule, users limit themselves to a quick look at the material, often focusing on words, phrases, paragraphs that interest them.

It is important to consider these features of the environment when composing texts for online publication and making web pages suitable for quick browsing. To optimize the visual perception of the text, the structure of the material should be created taking into account certain rules. It is necessary to adapt the material to the online publication and reduce its volume by 50%. Therefore, some experts describe the style of writing texts for online publications as abbreviated. The main information load is placed on the headings, the first and last paragraphs, as well as the first sentences of each paragraph. In online material, you should follow the principle that one paragraph is one complete thought. In addition, the structure of sentences is required to be very simple. It would be nice to break the text into separate parts using subtitles. To draw attention to paragraphs with main sentences, it is better to distinguish the font with a different color or pattern.

Even during the design phase of the publication, it is important to consider the space around the text that is necessary for comfortable reading. Also, it is necessary to ensure that the material is understandable for the reader, so the image and text are decorated with contrasting colors. A template with minimal contrast is used as the interface of the page. Using videos along with images for the interface will satisfy the current demand. Here it is better to avoid pictures without emotion.

In our study, the interface of the social network, the feature of providing information, etc. according to the criteria, a survey was conducted among students (Figure 2).

155 students participated in the survey. 87.2% of respondents said they like Instagram. In second place are TikTok (5.1%) and YouTube (5.1%), and lastly Facebook (2.6%).

Fig. 2. Popular social network among Kazakh students

Currently, a popular social network among young people and adults is Instagram. Everyone has a network, which is considered a symbol of aesthetics and beauty. That is why this social network has a great influence in forming image and reputation. In this regard, the Instagram page of any university has more readers than other networks.

Fig. 3. A popular social network indicator among foreign students

As the number of users increases, the scope of the social network expands, and ways of using it for various purposes are formed. Today, networks that have completely taken ownership of the process of information distribution have a high value in advertising distribution. The number of people who write a single post on Facebook and Instagram and earn a lot of money is increasing day by day.

Another popular social network among students is Instagram, so it is necessary for universities to work more in this direction. There is very little information on the official pages of many universities, and the latest news is often reported late. In order to be ahead of competing universities, it is necessary to pay special attention to networks, not just the university website. Where there is competition, quality increases. In this context, «In your opinion, which international network should be developed best by universities?» survey was conducted (Figure 4).

Fig. 4. «In your opinion, which social network should be better developed by universities?» the result of the survey

As we can see from the picture, students need to develop Instagram. It is also effective for recruitment. Broadcasting and providing information seems to be a common task for many people. Nowadays, with the help of mobile phones, information can be quickly accessed by quickly spreading the news from the scene. This is a nice feature. There are two sides to any phenomenon. We must also consider the dark side of the social network. Since it is possible to post information online through a personal account, there are cases of unverified, false information, and even information dissemination with the purpose of intentionally harming someone. In addition to personal safety, information, messages, and special group gatherings that are dangerous at the state level are also being conducted on social networks. It is difficult to prevent this by law. Since the law is weak, network maintenance requires a competent specialist. In particular, it is better that the management of the university network is entrusted not to a student, but to a specific employee. At this point, «If you were the head of the university, which social network would you ban in the university?» a survey was conducted. Taking into account the authenticity and value of the information, 77.8 percent of the respondents answered that they would ban the TikTok network in universities (Figure 5).

Fig. 5. A network that needs to be banned

It is necessary to be literate in order to be immune to current social conditions, information flow, and ideology. In today's information space, we can see that political

decisions and plans, the interests of business groups are interconnected and sometimes push each other. An ordinary person should be able to distinguish this situation. At the same time, it should be at a level that can be differentiated according to one's life, values and spiritual needs, as well as one's pocket.

In the research work, a study was made of the pages of educational institutions that train specialists in the field of media - journalists in this field. M.V. The Instagram blog of the Lomonosov Moscow State University, faculty of surrealism is regularly maintained. The interface is focused on the main color of the university logo. In the pictures and videos of the posts, blue color is emphasized a lot. But, the page is unsystematic, there is no uniformity, no attention is paid to art at all. The genre of photojournalism is taught in the specialty of journalism. We believe that this topic should be given special attention in the page.

Al-Farabi Kazakh National University, Journalism Faculty's blog on Instagram is also offline. Most of the awards and congratulations are given special importance, not the events taking place in the faculty. As if he wants to show only the proud points of the faculty.

The Instagram page of the Faculty of Journalism of the National University of Uzbekistan named after MirzoUlugbek has significantly fewer readers than the pages of other educational institutions. Other online links of the institution of interest are indicated for those interested. The page contains only the latest news.

Conclusions. There should be no room for complicated interfaces or questionable content in managing a mobile blog for higher education. In order to create an image, the most important and prominent should be left in the visual materials. The main value of any web service is speed. At this point, experts make a mistake, thinking that sites, social network pages will remain unchanged and do not depend on formats and devices. Readers and listeners expect information from the mobile version that they get in the big screen version. Therefore, according to the results of the research, every specialist in the field of SMM, whether he is a master of mobilography or a copywriter, should be able to use modern technologies. The technological capabilities of developed countries are developing at a rapid pace, whether they look at the information and communication environment of the world mass media and higher education institutions. Our educational institutions are not vulnerable, but the demand from customers is not increasing. Consumers are simply accepting innovation. The transformation of communicative environment and mass media is creating a new society. This field requires in-depth scientific qualitative and quantitative research.

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